

GENDER-RESPONSIVE MATERIAL FOR SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL ORAL COMMUNICATION

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Gender-Responsive Material for Senior High School Oral Communication

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Abstract

The main purpose of this study was to determine the efficacy of gender-responsive material for Oral communication as a pedagogical tool to improve the performance level of communication of the grade 11 students at Tingub National High School of Tingub, Mandaue City, Cebu, Philippines during the school year 2019-2020. It endeavored to assist Oral Communication teachers to assess the existing available DepEd-mandated materials and find more unique and innovative ways to sustain and retain students' interest in improved oral communication skills. It utilized a descriptive-normative design wherein the selected Grade 11 students having Oral Communication subject were able to answer the researcher-made questionnaires in the form of FGD and by drawing out their perceptions of the acceptability of the gender-responsive material after it was implemented and administered to evaluate their conversational skills. The findings demonstrate the following: sub-problem # 1 shows a Very Satisfactory performance level on the three learning competencies; sub-problem # 2 reveals the respondents' lived experiences and their perceptions toward the material; sub-problem # 3 displays the respondents' perceived level of acceptability in terms of content, comprehensibility, user-friendliness & functionality which have a High Acceptability level and sub-problem # 4 illustrates that the acceptability level of materials does not have a significant relationship with their performance level in the three identified competencies, however, it still shows a favorable result. Hence, gender-responsive learning materials in Oral Communication are beneficial in improving their speaking competencies because of their high level of acceptance despite the material's novelty and uniqueness.

Keywords: *english teaching, gender-responsiveness, descriptive-normative, level of acceptability, performance level, philippines*

Introduction

Gender inequality has long been a pervasive issue, influencing social structures, opportunities, and personal identities worldwide. In the context of education, gender bias in learning materials has hindered students' development, limiting their aspirations and understanding of their potential. These biases are evident in textbooks, classroom content, and language, subtly reinforcing traditional gender roles that restrict both male and female students. While various reforms have sought to address these disparities, including the implementation of Republic Act No. 10533 (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013), which advocates for gender-responsive educational materials, gender bias remains a persistent problem.

The Philippines Department of Education (DepEd) strengthened this initiative with DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2017, mandating the inclusion of gender-sensitive curriculum and teaching materials. Despite these efforts, gender stereotypes continue to permeate educational resources, especially in English language textbooks, where traditional gender roles are often reinforced. These biases, often presenting males as authoritative and intelligent and females in passive roles, shape students' self-perceptions and their interactions with others, ultimately influencing academic outcomes and social development.

This study was grounded in Stephen Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis, which underscores the importance of emotional and psychological factors in language acquisition. According to Krashen, motivation, anxiety, and self-confidence affect how well students engage with learning materials. Gender-biased content can evoke negative emotional responses, potentially hindering students' emotional engagement and language learning. On the other hand, gender-responsive materials that promote inclusivity may encourage positive emotional engagement, leading to improved communication skills.

Research has shown that gender-biased textbooks are not just an abstract issue; they have tangible effects on students' academic and social experiences. Studies by UNESCO (2017) have documented the persistence of male-dominated narratives in educational resources, which reinforce stereotypical gender roles and limit students' academic identities. Given these challenges, it is crucial to investigate whether gender-responsive materials can foster a more inclusive learning environment and improve students' academic outcomes, particularly in oral communication skills.

The Philippine government has made substantial efforts to address gender inequity through programs like the Women's EDGE Plan (2013–2016), which focuses on reducing gender-based violence and discrimination in educational settings. Additionally, the 2016 National Baseline Study on Violence Against Children highlighted the disproportionate discrimination faced by LGBT youth in schools, underscoring the need for gender-sensitive curricula that promote equality and inclusivity.

Research Questions

Despite ongoing efforts through Republic Act No. 10533 and DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2017, gender biases persist in educational resources, especially in English language textbooks. These biases likely affect students' emotional engagement, academic performance,

and social interactions. While gender-responsive materials have been promoted to address these issues, there is insufficient research on their impact, particularly on students' oral communication skills and their understanding of gender equality.

This study aimed to evaluate the impact of gender-responsive materials on Grade 11 students' oral communication skills. Specifically, it explored how these materials influenced students' attitudes toward gender equality, their communication performance, and their emotional engagement with the content. By addressing the emotional and academic effects of gender biases, the research sought to provide insights into how gender-responsive materials can enhance both communication skills and inclusivity in the classroom. The study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. How did the use of gender-responsive materials affect students' performance in:
 - 1.1. responding appropriately to speech acts;
 - 1.2. demonstrating sensitivity to gendered communication contexts; and
 - 1.3. identifying communication strategies used by speakers?
2. What were the lived experiences of students using gender-responsive materials in oral communication?
 - 2.1. how did exposure to gender-sensitive materials raise awareness of gender equality;
 - 2.2. how did students engage with diverse gender perspectives in the materials; and
 - 2.3. how adaptable were students in responding to different gender representations?
3. How acceptable were the gender-responsive materials in terms of:
 - 3.1. content relevance, inclusivity, and respect;
 - 3.2. comprehensibility and accessibility of gender-related concepts; and
 - 3.3. usability and effectiveness in teaching oral communication?
4. Was there a significant relationship between students' performance and their perceived acceptability of gender-responsive materials?
5. What recommendations can be made for developing an improved Gender-Responsive Material?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-normative research design to evaluate the effectiveness of gender-responsive materials in teaching Oral Communication. Descriptive evaluative research designs are commonly used to assess the value of specific materials or programs (Villanueva, 2013). The study aimed to determine whether these materials effectively enhanced students' oral communication competencies. The design provided essential insights into the efficacy of the materials and allowed for a detailed examination of their impact on student performance.

Respondents

The study targeted 50 Grade 11 students from the General Academic Strand (GAS), Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM), and Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) sections. These students were selected randomly, ensuring they fit the specific characteristics required for the study, as outlined by Del Selge (2016). The sample was chosen to represent the wider Grade 11 student population for measuring their perceptions of the module and their oral communication performance.

Instrument

To measure the students' attitudes towards the task-based gender-responsive module, the researcher adapted Krashen's (2016) Attitude Test in Language Learning. The instrument assessed three key competencies: responding to speech acts, demonstrating sensitivity to socio-cultural aspects of communication, and identifying strategies for effective idea conveyance. The module included rubrics and criteria for evaluation.

In addition to the questionnaire, 15 students were randomly selected from the 50 to answer an open-ended survey that gathered their opinions, insights, and lived experiences regarding the gender-responsive materials. A focused group discussion was also conducted to obtain more detailed information about their interactions with their peers.

Procedure

The following steps were taken to gather data:

Initial Permission: A letter was sent to the school principal to request approval for the study. Upon approval, letters were distributed to the student participants, explaining the study's purpose and their role.

Orientation: A methodical orientation was conducted to guide students through the study's procedures.

Material Creation: The researcher designed the gender-responsive module.

Trial Run: The module was tested with the target students, followed by data collection on their performance and attitudes toward the material.

Data Collection and Analysis: After the trial, the researcher gathered and analyzed the data to determine the effectiveness and students' experiences. The findings were then used to suggest revisions for the module.

Data Analysis

Several statistical methods were used to analyze the data:

Weighted Mean: This measure was used to assess the students' performance after using the gender-responsive materials. The scores were averaged to determine overall performance, and the results were categorized based on a performance rubric.

Pearson's Correlation Coefficient: This statistical test was used to evaluate the relationship between students' attitudes toward the module and their performance. The Pearson correlation was calculated to determine the strength of the relationship between the two variables.

For problem 3, Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to determine the relationship between students' performance and their perceived level of acceptability, with a significance level set at 0.05.

Results and Discussion

Performance Level of Students in Oral Communication

The students' performance in various oral communication competencies was assessed based on the weighted means and standard deviations of each competency. As summarized in Table 1, the following results were found for the competencies:

Table 1. Performance Level of the Students in Oral Communication

Competencies	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Category
Responding Effectively to Speech Acts	3.07	0.33	Very Satisfactory
Demonstrating Sensitivity to Socio-cultural Dimensions of Communication	2.96	0.48	Very Satisfactory
Identifying Strategies Used by the Speaker to Convey His Message	2.94	0.48	Very Satisfactory

According to the performance rating scale, the students demonstrated "Very Satisfactory" performance across all three competencies, with weighted means ranging from 2.94 to 3.07.

Perceived Acceptability of the Learning Resources

The perceived acceptability of the gender-responsive learning materials was evaluated based on four criteria: content, comprehensibility, user-friendliness, and functionality. As shown in Table 3, the students rated all criteria as "Very Acceptable," with the following results:

Table 3. Perceived Level of Acceptability

Criteria for the Acceptability Level	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Content	3.48	0.09	Very Acceptable
Comprehensibility	3.51	0.07	Very Acceptable
User-Friendliness	3.67	0.16	Very Acceptable
Functionality	3.60	0.12	Very Acceptable
Total Grand Mean	3.57	0.09	Very Acceptable

The total grand mean of 3.57 indicates that the students found the learning materials to be "Very Acceptable" across all aspects evaluated.

Relationship Between Performance and Acceptability

The relationship between the students' performance levels and the acceptability of the learning resources was analyzed using Pearson's correlation coefficient. The results, summarized in Table 4, show the computed correlation and the critical value at the 0.05 significance level.

Table 4. Relationship Between Level of Acceptability of the Learning Resource and Performance Level

Variable Relationship	Critical <i>r</i> value	Computed <i>r</i> value	Decision	Interpretation
Acceptability of Learning Resource & Performance Level	0.1872	-0.0776	Failed to reject H_0	No correlation at 0.05 level of significance

The computed *r* value of -0.0776 was compared to the critical *r* value of 0.1872. Since the computed *r* value was smaller in magnitude than the critical value, the null hypothesis (H_0) was not rejected, indicating that there is no significant correlation between the students' perceived acceptability of the learning resources and their performance in oral communication.

This result suggests that, despite the students' positive perception of the learning materials, there is no statistically significant

relationship between how acceptable they found the materials and their performance levels in oral communication. The findings imply that the students' perceptions of the resource's acceptability do not directly influence their performance outcomes in this context.

Several factors could explain this lack of correlation, such as individual differences in learner motivation, prior knowledge, or external influences like teaching methods. Additionally, while the learning resources were deemed acceptable, the lack of a strong relationship may suggest that other factors, such as classroom dynamics, peer interaction, or instructional quality, may play a more significant role in influencing students' performance.

In conclusion, the analysis showed no statistically significant correlation between the level of acceptability of the learning resources and the students' performance levels. This highlights the complexity of factors affecting student performance, suggesting that while acceptability may impact the learning experience, it is not the sole determinant of academic success in oral communication.

The study aimed to explore the performance level of Grade 11 students in Oral Communication, their lived experiences with Gender-Responsive Learning Materials, the acceptability level of these materials, and the potential relationship between their perceptions of the materials and their performance. Using a descriptive normative research design, the study gathered valuable insights into students' responses toward the integration of gender-diverse materials in the curriculum.

The findings revealed that the students' performance in Oral Communication had a grand mean of 2.99 with a standard deviation of 0.40, categorized as "Very Satisfactory." This indicates that the students performed well across various competencies, including responding effectively to speech acts, demonstrating sensitivity to socio-cultural dimensions of communication, and identifying strategies used by speakers to convey messages. These results suggest that, overall, the students met the expected standards for effective oral communication, indicating that they were capable of engaging with the content and demonstrating proficiency in the key skills assessed.

The students' lived experiences with the Gender-Responsive Learning Materials were categorized into three primary themes: awareness, acceptability, and adaptability. The theme of awareness reflected how students came to recognize the importance of gender diversity and inclusivity, which was especially evident in their reactions to lessons addressing gender identities beyond the male-female binary. Several students expressed how these lessons challenged their previous understandings of gender roles, leading to greater awareness of gender diversity. The acceptability theme emphasized the students' positive reception of the materials, with many reporting that the content was engaging, relevant, and thought-provoking. This acceptance was further reflected in the acceptability level of the materials, which had a grand mean of 3.57 and a standard deviation of 0.09, described as "Very Acceptable." This high acceptability score suggests that the students found the materials both useful and relevant to their educational needs. Finally, the theme of adaptability highlighted how students adjusted to the introduction of gender-diverse content and embraced its integration into their learning. Many students expressed that the newness of the materials offered them a valuable opportunity to engage with contemporary issues and to develop a deeper understanding of gender-related topics.

However, the study also found no significant correlation between the students' performance and their perception of the acceptability of the Gender-Responsive Learning Materials. The computed r value of -0.0776 was lower than the critical r value of 0.1872 , leading to the failure to reject the null hypothesis and indicating no significant relationship between the two variables. This lack of correlation suggests that, despite the students' positive perceptions of the materials, their level of acceptance did not have a measurable impact on their performance in oral communication. This finding aligns with previous literature, which suggests that student performance can be influenced by multiple factors beyond the perceived quality or acceptability of learning materials, including individual learning preferences, teaching strategies, and external influences such as peer support or prior knowledge.

In light of this, the results also point to the complexity of educational outcomes, where students' engagement with the learning materials may not necessarily translate into immediate performance improvements. It is possible that other factors, such as student motivation, classroom dynamics, and instructional methods, play more significant roles in influencing performance outcomes. Therefore, while gender-responsive learning materials were positively accepted by students, their influence on actual performance levels appears to be indirect, mediated by various contextual factors.

Conclusions

The Gender-Responsive Learning Materials used in this study have proven effective in fostering students' awareness and acceptance of gender diversity, as well as in enhancing their speaking competencies in Oral Communication. The students demonstrated a high level of adaptability to the new content, and their overall performance in the competencies assessed was rated as "Very Satisfactory." While the acceptability of the materials was rated positively, there was no significant relationship found between their perceptions and their performance, indicating that other factors may be influencing the students' academic outcomes.

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed to further enhance the effectiveness of gender-responsive teaching strategies:

Experimental Studies on Gender-Responsive Materials: Future research should explore the use of gender-responsive materials across all English subjects, particularly in Oral Communication. An experimental design could help examine the direct effects of carefully

crafted materials that align with the three core learning competencies outlined in the Curriculum Guide (EN11/120C-Ifj-20, EN11/120C-Ifj-16, EN11/120C-Ibe-14).

Expand Thematic Experiences: The students' lived experiences with gender-responsive materials should be further examined to address potential limitations in the use of such materials, particularly in the context of activities, performance, and assessment tasks. This would ensure that gender-responsive materials are inclusive and cater to all students, including those who may be influenced by cultural or religious conservatism.

Gender-Inclusive Curriculum Workshops for Teachers: It is crucial to organize workshops and training sessions for teachers to enhance their awareness and knowledge of gender diversity. These workshops would help teachers apply gender-sensitive, gender-fair, and gender-responsive approaches in the classroom, enabling them to design and implement more inclusive teaching materials and strategies.

Strengthening the Link Between Performance and Teaching Strategies: Future studies should explore the relationship between students' performance and the diverse teaching strategies employed by educators. This would help establish a clearer connection between teaching practices and students' academic outcomes, especially in the context of a gender-diverse curriculum.

By implementing these recommendations, it is possible to further refine the integration of gender-responsive materials in education and better understand their impact on student performance and learning experiences.

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